

Supporting Information

Stoichiometric selective carbonylation of methane to acetic acid by chemical looping

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Figure S1. The gas product over TiO₂, Pt-TiO₂, Pt-HPW-TiO₂, Pt-HPW-TiO₂ in H₂O with CH₄ and CO and Pt-HPW-TiO₂ only with CO after reaction. General reaction conditions: 50 mg samples, 15 bar CH₄ (sample only with CO will be added 15 bar N₂), 1 bar CO, 175 °C, 2 h reaction time. In the case of test with water, 1 g of water has been added in the reactor.

Figure S2. Comparison of the AcOH synthesis performance of Pt-HPW-TiO₂ using either air or Ar as the regeneration atmosphere.

Figure S3. HAADF-STEM and corresponding EDS-mapping images of Pt-HPW-TiO₂ before reaction.

Figure S4. HAADF-STEM images of Pt-HPW-TiO₂ before reaction with demonstration of heteropolyacid units (circle)

Figure S5. HAADF-STEM images of Pt-HPW-TiO₂ before reaction

Figure S6. HAADF-STEM and corresponding EDS-mapping images of Pt-HPW-TiO₂ after reaction.

Figure S7. HAADF-STEM and corresponding EDS-mapping images of Pt-HPW-TiO₂ after regeneration.

Figure S8. The optimization of the reaction temperature and of material characteristics for acetic acid synthesis on Pt-HPW-TiO₂. General reaction conditions: 50 mg samples, 15 bar CH₄, 1 bar CO, 2 h reaction time.

Figure S9. The reference tests of different gas ratios on Pt-HPW-TiO₂. General reaction conditions: 50 mg samples, 175 °C, 2 h reaction time.

Figure S10. FTIR analysis of CO adsorption with subsequent desorption over prepared PtHPW-TiO₂

Figure S11. FTIR analysis of Py adsorption over TiO₂, Pt-HPW-TiO₂ before and after reaction and after regeneration.

Figure S12. FTIR-monitored thermal desorption of acetic acid on Pt-HPW-TiO₂.

Figure S13. ^1H - ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR spectra of treating TiO_2 and insoluble ammonia salt of HPW with glacial AcOH.

Figure S14. ^{17}O NMR analysis of liquid solution after hydrolysis using H_2^{17}O .

$^1\text{H}\{^{17}\text{O}\}$ S-RESPDOR MAS

after reaction washed with labeled H_2^{17}O

Figure S15. $^1\text{H}\{^{17}\text{O}\}$ S-RESPDOR MAS NMR spectra without (s_0) and with (S) ^{17}O saturation pulse and corresponding difference ($\Delta S = S_0 - S$) of dehydrated Pt-HPW- TiO_2 material after reaction and hydrolysis by $50\mu\text{l}$ labeled H_2^{17}O with SR4_1^2 recoupling time of $100\mu\text{s}$ and 2.2ms .

Figure S16. Configuration screening for the reactant and the product states, with the relative energies of the various adsorption modes at Pt-HPW-TiO₂.

Figure S17. Reaction intermediate and transition state balls & sticks model related to acetic acid formation from CO and water (see reaction path in Fig. 5 of the manuscript).

Figure S18. Literature comparisons of the AcOH concentration and AcOH selectivity in liquidphase. References are as follows: PdSO₄ (1), Rh-ZSM-5 (0.5 wt.%) (3), Rh-ZSM-5 (0.1 wt.%) (4), Fe-BN/ZSM-5 (6), Ce-UiO-Cu(OH) (8), (Pt/NPW)/TiO₂ (9), Ir complex /SBA-15 (10), Rh₁/pMOF (11), Pd₁-ZSM-5 (12), Ni-ZSM-5 (13).

Table S1. Comparison of the existing conversion routes for the synthesis of acetic acid from methane

Name	Reaction conditions	AcOH Conc. (wt. %)	AcOH Conc. (mmol/L)	Liquid-phase AcOH Select. (%)	Ref.
PdSO ₄	20 mM PdSO ₄ , 96% H ₂ SO ₄ , 180 °C, 7 h	0.49	82	67.9	1
Cu-mordenite	1.5 g samples, 50 mL/min O ₂ , 10 mL/min CH ₄ , 200 °C, 0.5 h	-	-	48.7	2
Rh-ZSM-5 (0.5 wt.%)	20 mg samples, 2 bar O ₂ , 5 bar CO, 20 bar CH ₄ , 20 mL H ₂ O, 150 °C, 3 h	0.13	21.30	70.1	3
Rh-ZSM-5 (0.1 wt.%)	28 mg samples, 8 bar O ₂ , 10 bar CO, 50 bar CH ₄ , 10 mL H ₂ O, 150 °C, 12 h	0.5	84	70.1	4
Au-ZSM-5	100 mg samples, 1 bar O ₂ , 2.5 bar CO, 20.7 bar CH ₄ , 15 mL H ₂ O, 240 °C, 4 h	0.003	0.5	12.7	5
Fe-BN/ZSM-5	20 mg samples, 5 bar CO, 25 bar CH ₄ , 654 μmol H ₂ O ₂ , 20 mL H ₂ O, 50 °C, 6 h	0.01	1.2	57	6
PdO/Pd-WO ₃	100 mg samples, CH ₄ and H ₂ O flow, 3h	-	-	91.6	7
Ce-UiO-Cu(OH)	3.7 mg samples, 6 bar O ₂ , 30 bar CH ₄ , 8 mL H ₂ O, 115 °C, 40 h	0.93	155	99.9	8
(Pt/NPW)/TiO ₂	50 mg samples, 1 bar CO, 10 bar CH ₄ , 10 mL H ₂ O, 25 °C, 400W Hg-Xe lamp, 60 h	0.03	5.7	90.6	9
Ir complex /SBA-15	15 mg samples, 4 bar O ₂ , 5 bar CO, 19 bar CH ₄ , 15 mL H ₂ O, 150 °C, 3 h	0.06	10.2	65.6	10
Rh ₁ /pMOF	20 mg samples, 4 bar O ₂ , 5 bar CO, 15 bar CH ₄ , 20 mL H ₂ O; 150 °C, 3 h	0.43	70.9	83.8	11
Pd ₁ -ZSM-5	25 mg samples, 25 °C, 15 mL 0.6 M H ₂ O ₂ , 30 bar CH ₄ , 20 bar CO, 0.5 h	0.01	1.3	78.3	12
Ni-ZSM-5	20 mg samples, 5 bar of CO, 25 bar CH ₄ , 654 μmol H ₂ O ₂ , 20 mL H ₂ O, 50 °C, 10 h	0.02	2.9	82.3	13
Pt-HPW-TiO ₂	1 g samples, 1 bar CO, 15 bar CH ₄ , 0.1 mL H ₂ O; 175 °C, 2 h	1.06	177.3	99	This work

Table S2. ICP-OES analysis of metal content

Sample	Co (wt. %)	Cu(wt. %)	Pd(wt. %)	Rh(wt. %)	Pt(wt. %)	W(wt. %)
Pt-HPW-TiO ₂	-	-	-	-	0.202	0.159
Pt-HPW-TiO ₂ after reaction	-	-	-	-	0.174	0.15
Pt-HPW-TiO ₂ after regeneration	-	-	-	-	0.167	0.147
Rh-HPW-TiO ₂	-	-	-	0.247	-	-
Pd-HPW-TiO ₂	-	-	0.226	-	-	-
Cu-HPW-TiO ₂	-	0.162	-	-	-	-
Co-HPW-TiO ₂	0.194	-	-	-	-	-

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